

Multidisciplinary Surgical Research Annals

<https://msra.online/index.php/Journal/about>

Volume 3, Issue 4(2025)

Effect Of Replacing Maize Grain With Date Waste Meal (DWM) On Growth Performance, Carcass Yield And Blood Chemistry Of Japanese Quails

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Article Details

Keywords: Quails, Date Waste meal, Maize, By-Product, Non-Conventional Feed Resources.

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ABSTRACT

Quails are fast growing poultry birds. These are reared for meat and egg production. However, its cost effective production depends on balancing diets. The incorporation of non-conventional feed ingredients can alleviate the diet cost for profitable farming. In this context, present study conducted to know the growth performance and blood profile of quails by replacing Maize grain with Date Waste Meal (DWM). Chicks of Japanese quail (n=120) were purchased from a private company in Karachi. After recording of initial weight, the birds were separated into four groups (A, B, C, and D) at random. Three replicates were made from each group, each having (10) birds. Four experimental diets (1, 2, 3 and 4) were prepared and fed to groups A, B, C, and D, respectively. Group A served as control group in which no DWM was incorporated. Group C showed maximum feed intake ($P < 0.05$) (4930.08 ± 22.23^a) whilst minimum in group D (4376.25 ± 24.90^c). Similar to feed intake, body weight recorded maximum in group C (3695.79 ± 38.45^a) whilst minimum by group A (2490.23 ± 30.76^c) and D (2503.45 ± 64.80^c). Group wise FCR was recorded least by group C (1.34 ± 0.23^a) whilst highest by groups A (1.78 ± 1.19^c) and D (1.76 ± 1.53^c). Total protein level was recorded same ($P > 0.05$) among groups B (50.85 ± 1.01^a), A (50.51 ± 0.95^a) and C (561.09 ± 16.18^a) whilst the minimum ($P < 0.05$) in group D (48.11 ± 0.44^b). Total lipids recorded higher in the group C (561.09 ± 16.18^a), B (548.10 ± 10.80^a) and A (540.20 ± 18.21^a) whilst the minimum recorded in the group D (510.76 ± 9.27^b). In total cholesterol, blood calcium, and blood phosphate, all groups A, B, C and D showed statistically similar levels however, blood glucose level recorded higher in group C (3.94 ± 0.17^a) whilst the minimum in group D (2.89 ± 0.11^d). It is concluded that Japanese quails showed maximum growth performance (feed intake, weight gain and feed conversion ratio) on diet containing 25% DWM by replacing with maize grain. Therefore, DWM can be added at 25% level in the diets of Japanese quails.

INTRODUCTION:

Quail is one of the popular livestock that contributes in fulfilling the animal protein need for human population (Suherman et al., 2015). Quails belong to order Galliformes and family Phasianidae. Among the family Phasianidae, Japanese Quails are very popular for domestication (Ani et al., 2009). Due to many special characteristics such as low generation interval, minimum ration requirement and easy domestication, quail farming is expanding gradually. Japanese quails are usually reared for meat and egg production however, it is being used as bio-tool for research studies (Roger, 2013).

Many expensive feed ingredients are being used in poultry feed industries now-a-days. About 85% of maize and maize by-product are often utilized as a feed ingredient for preparation livestock and poultry ration (Flachowsky et al., 2012). Tenenbaum (2008) added that corn strains are not only utilized by farm animals but also for beverages, industrial starch, biofuels and human edible foods. Production of large quantity of corn grains varieties is capital intensive pursuit (Morne, 2017).

Dates and its wastes are potential sources of non-conventional energy feed. Many developing countries produce Date palm and their fruits which play an important role in arid and semi-arid lands as a ration. Date fruit plays an important role in boosting immunity of humans. It contains carotenoids, minerals, vitamins, polyphenols, and rich dietary fibers. It is also beneficial for health improvement. The global date palm production is estimated as 8166014 metric tons. Iran alone (second major producer) produces about 14.5% of world production while Egypt on top produces about 19.5% of world production (FAO, 2018). Among all date producing countries Pakistan ranked 7th in 2011. More than 150 types of dates are being produced in Pakistan specially in Sindh, Balochistan and in few districts of Punjab namely Aseel, Zahidi, Begum Dhakki, Jangi, Khudravi and Halavi etc. Of these, Dhakki and Aseel are highly produced. These dates are classified as soft, dry, and semi-soft (Ismail et al., 2008). Pakistan produces mostly semi-dry dates which are rich in carbohydrates 81-88% (containing glucose, fructose and sucrose), 5-8.5% of dietary fiber, and other nutrients are in few quantities (Nadeem et al., 2011). It is estimated that 20% of date produced in Pakistan are not considered for human use and are categorized as waste due to their poor quality.

Various categories of date waste are as syrup, unused and half grown fruits, puree, paste, date pits as flour, as powder, and as a liquid extract (Kulkarni et al., 2010; Baliga et al., 2011; Diab & Ela, 2012; Martin-Sanchez et al., 2013; Jridi et al., 2015; Ambigaipalan & Shahidi, 2015; Di Cagno et al., 2017), respectively. Abbas et al. (2005) reported that date waste have lysine (0.04 to 0.13%), methionine + cysteine (0.07 to 0.12%), metabolizable energy (2321 to 3050 kcal/kg), crude fat (1.1–3.9%), carbohydrate (total sugars, 44–88%), crude fiber (2.4–16.0%) and crude protein (2.4–4.0%). Although these researches have indicated the importance of use of date waste in diet of quails (Kamel et al., 2020) however, inclusion of DWM up to 20% in poultry diets does not have any adverse effect on growth performance of birds (Attia & Al-Harhi, 2015).

The feeding of date waste meal may also affect carcass quality and biochemical parameter in poultry birds. Length and width of carcass are the key feature of meat quality in poultry. Age, strain of birds and sex are the main factors which affect the quality of carcass in Japanese quails. Moisture and fat content of carcass can be influenced by the age of bird. With the age of bird, the fat percentage increases while the moisture content decreases.

In Balochistan and Sindh, date trees are grown for commercial production and marketing. During harvesting, high level of non-edible dates are wasted for no use. These wasted dates have good potential to be used in poultry and livestock diets. Based on these facts, this present study is planned to incorporate non-edible wasted dates by replacing conventional maize grain in the diet to study growth performance, blood profile and carcass yield. The following were the objectives of present study.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study on utilization of non-convention feed source i.e., date waste meal in quails diet was carried out to know its effect on growth performance and other carcass parameter. This feeding trial was conducted in

Animal Nutrition Lab. 111 of Lasbela University, Uthal. The details are described below.

Feeding experiment

Chicks of Japanese quail (n=120) were purchased from a private company in Karachi. After recording of initial weight, the birds were separated into four groups (A, B, C, and D) at random. Three replicates were made from each group, each having (10) birds. The bird's standard raising conditions i.e., temperature, humidity, and light were maintained throughout the twenty-eight (28) day study period. For each group, weekly feed consumption and weight gain were recorded. At the end research FCR was calculated using data of weight gain and feed intake.

Four experimental diets (1, 2, 3 and 4) were prepared and fed to groups A, B, C, and D, respectively, with varying amounts of date waste meal instead of maize grain shown in (table 3.1). Water and the diets were offered adlibitum. Keeping the recommendations of NRC (1994) the levels of protein and energy were prepared. From each replicate three birds were randomly chosen and slaughtered at last of the experiment in order to record the dressing percentage and carcass weight.

Feed intake

Birds were fed twice daily, and refused feed from each feeder of each group was collected, weighted and calculated daily. Following formula used for this practice:

$$\text{Feed intake (g/b/d)} = \frac{\text{Total feed provided} - \text{total refused feed}}{\text{Total birds (\%)}}$$

Weight gain

At the arrival of chicks at Poultry Experimental Station, electrical weighting scale was used to weight the chicks, after that quails were weighted on weekly basis till the end of trail.

FCR

Feed conversion ratio was calculated with the following formula.

$$\text{FCR} = \frac{\text{Total feed intake}}{\text{Total live body weight}}$$

Laboratory Analysis:

At the end of the study, blood samples from nine selected birds from each group (three from each replica) were taken to determine the blood profiles. Centrifuging the serum at 3000 rpm for 10 minutes produced the serum, which was then kept at -18 0C until analysis. The total protein, total cholesterol, total lipids, phosphorus, calcium and glucose were determined with reference to the procedure adopted by Aggoor et al. (2000).

Statistical Analysis

Collected data weight gain, feed intake, carcass yield, FCR, blood chemistry and dressing percentage were analyzed statically using ANOVA (Analysis of Variance) technique (Steel et al., 1998) under completely randomized design. By applying Duncan's multiple range test (Duncan, 1955) for significance the difference among means were compared.

Results

Feed intake of Japanese Quails on experimental diets

This chapter describes results of feeding experiment on knowing growth performance, dressing percentage and blood chemistry of birds fed with different levels of non-conventional feed resource (date waste meal)

by replacing main conventionally used feed ingredient (corn grain) in diets of Japanese quails. In this context, the Table 4.1 shows data of weekly feed intake of different groups which were significant different ($P<0.05$). The data of week-1 showed highest feed intake by Group C (656 ± 07.89) whilst least feed intake recorded in group A (620 ± 8.90) and B (631 ± 10.15). Same trend recorded during week-2 where group C again showed highest feed intake (970 ± 12.09) however, least feed intake (940 ± 14.21) was exhibited by birds of group D. Likewise, during week 3 and 4, group C continued maximum feed intake (1474 ± 8.89 , 1830 ± 12.56 , respectively) while group D remained with lowest feed intake (1248 ± 12.54 , 1563 ± 20.19 , respectively) along with group A during week-4 (1553 ± 12.77).

Table 4.1 Feed intake g/week of Japanese Quails fed on four experimental diets

Group	Week			
	1	2	3	4
A (0% DWS)	620 ± 8.90^b	916 ± 15.98^c	1306 ± 14.43^c	1553 ± 12.77^c
B (15% DWM)	631 ± 10.15^b	901 ± 18.92^b	1384 ± 11.96^b	1615 ± 17.10^b
C (25% DWM)	656 ± 07.89^a	970 ± 12.09^a	1474 ± 8.89^a	1830 ± 12.56^a
D (35% DWM)	625 ± 10.73^b	940 ± 14.21^d	1248 ± 12.54^d	1563 ± 20.19^c
Level of Sig.	$P<0.05$	$P<0.05$	$P<0.05$	$P<0.05$

The superscripts with different alphabets within column are statistically different at 0.05 level

Weight gain of Japanese Quails fed on experimental diets

The Table 4.2 shows data of weekly live body weight of different groups of birds which were significantly different ($P<0.05$). The Day-1 data shows that initial body weight was statistically similar ($P>0.05$) among all groups. At Day-7, group C (418 ± 7.01) showed highest body weight while group D (325 ± 6.69) and A (325 ± 5.22) showed least body weight. At Day-14, group C continued its growth with maximum body weight (910 ± 4.82) followed by B (780 ± 5.55) whilst group A (625 ± 7.91) showed least weight. At Day-21, group C (1825 ± 3.23) again showed maximum weight gain while the minimum was recorded in group A, B and D (1480 ± 3.48 , 1510 ± 4.67 , 1520 ± 4.67), respectively. Likewise, at Day-28, group C showed maximum weight gain (3695 ± 3.19) however, the minimum weigh gain was recorded in group A and D (2490 ± 9.44 , 2503 ± 7.99), respectively.

Table 4.2 Weight gain of Japanese Quails fed on experimental diets

Group	Day				
	1	7	14	21	28
A (0% DWM)	189 ± 3.90	335 ± 5.22^c	625 ± 7.91^d	1480 ± 3.48^b	2490 ± 7.99^c
B (15% DWM)	187 ± 4.03	385 ± 8.89^b	780 ± 5.55^b	1510 ± 4.67^b	3290 ± 2.76^b
C (25% DWM)	190 ± 3.97	418 ± 7.01^a	910 ± 4.82^a	1825 ± 3.23^a	3695 ± 3.19^a
D (35% DWM)	188 ± 4.59	325 ± 6.69^c	648 ± 10.91^c	1520 ± 4.09^b	2503 ± 9.44^c
Level of Sig.	N.S	$P<0.05$	$P<0.05$	$P<0.05$	$P<0.05$

The superscripts with different alphabets within column are statistically different at 0.05 level

Feed conversion ratio (FCR) of Japanese Quails fed on four experimental diets

The Table 4.3 shows data of weekly feed conversion ratio of different groups which were significantly different ($P<0.05$). During Week-1, the best FCR was recorded by group C (1.68 ± 0.18) whilst least good FCR was recorded by group D (2.27 ± 0.23). During Week-2, groups B and C showed better FCR (1.56 ± 0.79 , 1.58 ± 0.44 , respectively) whilst the maximum FCR value (least good) was exhibited by groups D and A (2.09 ± 0.31 , 2.19 ± 0.81 , respectively). The similar trend of good FCR performance was continued by group C during weeks 3 and 4 and least FCR by groups A and D during weeks 3 and 4.

Table 4.3 Feed conversion ratio (FCR) of Japanese Quails fed on four experimental diets

Groups	Week			
	1	2	3	4
A (0% DWM)	2.16 ± 0.17^c	2.19 ± 0.81^b	2.01 ± 0.23^b	1.38 ± 0.22^b
B (15% DWM)	1.72 ± 0.32^b	1.56 ± 0.79^a	1.54 ± 0.67^a	1.12 ± 0.44^a
C (25% DWM)	1.68 ± 0.18^a	1.58 ± 0.44^a	1.45 ± 0.11^a	1.09 ± 0.58^a
D (35% DWM)	2.27 ± 0.23^d	2.09 ± 0.31^b	1.92 ± 0.46^b	1.53 ± 0.30^b
Level of Sig.	$P<0.05$	$P<0.05$	$P<0.05$	$P<0.05$

The superscripts with different alphabets within column are statistically different at 0.05 level

Overall feed intake, body weight (g) and FCR of Japanese Quails on experimental diets

The Table 4.4 shows data of feed consumption, body weight and FCR of birds during study period. Group C showed maximum feed intake ($P<0.05$) (4930.08 ± 22.23) whilst minimum in group D (4376.25 ± 24.90). Similar to feed intake, body weight recorded maximum in group C (3695.79 ± 38.45) whilst minimum by group A (2490.23 ± 30.76) and D (2503.45 ± 64.80). Group wise FCR was recorded least by group C (1.34 ± 0.23) whilst highest by groups A (1.78 ± 1.19) and D (1.76 ± 1.53).

Table 4.4 Overall feed intake, body weight (g) and FCR of Japanese Quails on experimental diets

Groups	Feed Intake (g)	Body weight (g)	FCR
A (0% DWS)	4495.00 ± 20.81^b	2490.23 ± 30.76^c	1.78 ± 1.19^c
B (15% DWM)	4530.25 ± 18.93^b	3290.46 ± 22.15^b	1.66 ± 0.10^b
C (25% DWM)	4930.08 ± 22.23^a	3695.79 ± 38.45^a	1.34 ± 0.23^a
D (35% DWM)	4376.25 ± 24.90^c	2503.45 ± 64.80^c	1.76 ± 1.53^c
Significance Level	$P<0.05$	$P<0.05$	$P<0.05$

The superscripts with different alphabets within column are statistically different at 0.05 level

Pre and post slaughter body weight of Japanese Quails fed on experimental diets

The Table 4.5 shows data on different characteristics of dressing percentage in Japanese quails (group wise) fed on different levels of DWM. The significant differences ($P<0.05$) found in live weight, weight after slaughtering, carcass weight and carcass weight without visceral organs among all groups. Live weight recorded maximum in group C (106.05 ± 2.77) and B (103.0 ± 2.16) whilst lowest in D (86.10 ± 4.35). Same trend followed in other parameters i.e., weight-after-slaughter, carcass weight and carcass weight without

visceral organs from collected samples of birds from different groups.

Table 4.5 Pre and post slaughter body weight of Japanese Quails fed on experimental diets

Groups	LW	WAS
A (0% DWS)	98.0±4.98 ^{ab}	95.13±5.07 ^{ab}
B (15% DWM)	103.0±2.16 ^a	100.13±1.76 ^a
C (25% DWM)	106.05±2.77 ^a	103.38±2.88 ^a
D (35% DWM)	86.10±4.35 ^b	83.5.66±4.30 ^b
Level of Sig.	P<0.05	P<0.05

The superscripts with different alphabets within column are statistically different at 0.05 level

LW: Live weight; WAS: Weight after slaughtering; CW: Carcass weight; CWWVO: Carcass weight without visceral organs

Table 4.6 Carcass weight with and without visceral organs of Japanese Quails fed on experimental diets

The Table 4.6 shows data on different characteristics of dressing percentage in Japanese quails (group wise) fed on different levels of DWM. The significant differences (P<0.05) found in carcass weight and carcass weight without visceral organs among all groups. Carcass weight and carcass weight without visceral organs recorded maximum in group C (80.63±2.30^a, 62.75±2.80^a) and B (77.50±1.34^a, 60.12±2.56^a) whilst lowest in D (61.75±1.66^b, 43.12±1.42^b) respectively.

Table 4.6 Carcass weight with and without visceral organs of Japanese Quails fed on experimental diets

Groups	CW	CWWVO
A (0% DWS)	70.00±5.23 ^b	52.37±5.85 ^{ab}
B (15% DWM)	77.50±1.34 ^a	60.12±2.56 ^a
C (25% DWM)	80.63±2.30 ^a	62.75±2.80 ^a
D (35% DWM)	61.75±1.66 ^b	43.12±1.42 ^b
Level of Sig.	P<0.05	P<0.05

Blood profile of Japanese Quails on experimental diets

The Table 4.6 shows blood profile of Japanese quails (group wise). The significant differences (P<0.05) were recorded among different groups. Total protein level recorded maximum and same among groups B (50.85±1.01), A (50.51±0.95) and C (50.03±0.87) whilst the minimum total protein level recorded in the group D (48.11±0.44). Total lipids recorded higher in the group C (561.09±16.18), B (548.10±10.80) and A (540.20±18.21) whilst the minimum recorded in the group D (510.76±9.27). In total cholesterol, blood calcium, and blood phosphate, all groups A, B, C and D showed statistically similar levels however, blood glucose level recorded higher in group C (10.94±0.17) whilst the minimum in group D (9.89±0.11).

Table 4.7 Blood profile of Japanese Quails on experimental diets

Groups	Total Protein (g/L)	Total Lipids (mg/L)	Total Cholesterol (mmol/L)	Blood Glucose (mmol/L)	Blood Calcium (mg/dl)	Blood Phosphorus (mg/dl)
A (0% DWS)	50.51±0.95	540.20±18.21	1.80±0.05	10.94±0.17	10.0±0.5	1.0±0.1
B (15% DWM)	50.85±1.01	548.10±10.80	1.80±0.05	10.94±0.17	10.0±0.5	1.0±0.1
C (25% DWM)	50.03±0.87	561.09±16.18	1.80±0.05	10.94±0.17	10.0±0.5	1.0±0.1
D (35% DWM)	48.11±0.44	510.76±9.27	1.80±0.05	9.89±0.11	10.0±0.5	1.0±0.1

A DWM)	(0%	50.51±0.95 ^a	540.20±18.21 ^a	8.66±0.59	10.23±0.19 ^c	10.21±0.13	3.44±0.08
B DWM)	(15%	50.85±1.01 ^a	548.10±10.80 ^a	8.84±0.32	10.68±0.10 ^b	10.30±0.19	3.59±0.04
C DWM)	(25%	50.03±0.87 ^a	561.09±16.18 ^a	8.59±0.28	10.94±0.17 ^a	10.19±0.18	3.43±0.08
D DWM)	(35%	48.11±0.44 ^b	510.76±9.27 ^b	8.42±0.37	9.89±0.11 ^d	10.09±0.20	3.29±0.09
Level of Sig.		P<0.05	P<0.05	P>0.05	P<0.05	P>0.05	P>0.05

The superscripts with different alphabets within column are statistically different at 0.05 level

DISCUSSION

Food shortage and malnutrition are major issues in developing countries including Pakistan. Physical and mental health of the population is being adversely affected by malnutrition (Omikhoje et al., 2008). Protein is the major part of diet for growth and development. Its availability to ever increasing population is always stand as question for the researchers. In this connection, the scientists design their studies on birds and livestock so that speedy growth can be achieved and availability of quality protein to the population can be ensured in the form of meat at economical rates. Among poultry birds, the Japanese quail is fast growing common commercial bird. It is vibrant source for the production of meat (attain maturity within 4-5 weeks) and eggs (Hussain et al., 2013). In addition to that, there is need of continuous research studies particularly on least cast diets due to improved genetic selection as improved feeding will truly utilize the genetic potential of birds. The feed cost can be well managed by formulation of least cast balanced diets which decreases wastage of nutrients, labor and increases net income (Mosaad and Ibn, 2009). Further, the role of locally available non-conventional feed resources required to be explored so that more economical diets can be formulated and feed cost may be lessened. Hence, this study particularly focused on replacement of maize grain with locally available non-conventional feed resource i.e., date waste meal (DWM) to understand its influence on growth performance and blood profile.

Growth performance is of prime indicator in the profitable farming of poultry birds. During this study, data were obtained on feed intake, weight gain and feed conversion ratio of different groups fed varied levels of DWM. In our study we fed four different diets to birds by replacing major ingredient i.e., maize grain with date waste meal (DWM). The trend in feed intake and weight gain recorded increased with increase in inclusion level of date waste meal up to 25 percent. Likewise, feed conversion ratio minimum up to 25 % inclusion of DWM whilst it was statistically similar at zero and at 35% inclusion rate of DWM. In partial agreement to our findings, Attia et al. (2017) reported no difference in feed intake and FCR during 1-5 weeks of age by increasing DWM levels in the diets up to 20% while increasing DWM levels from 20 to 25 or 30% resulted significant (P< 0.01) increase in feed consumption and FCR compared with control and other dietary treatment groups. The partial difference of our findings with Attia et al. (2017) lies in levels of inclusion rate of DWM where we find increasing trend in feed intake, weight gain and FCR from 15% to 25 % up to experimental period of four weeks. The further increase of DWM (35%) decreased feed intake, weight gain and FCR. This difference of performance in both studies may be due to difference in genetic potential of birds, management practices, and nutritional as well as physical characteristics of date waste meal.

In our study, carcass yield was statically different among all groups. It was found that increasing the level of DWM from 15 % to 25% increased carcass weight and carcass weight without visceral organs. The zero level and inclusion level at 35% of DWM decreased both weight of carcass and weight of net weight of carcass (without visceral organs). Partially inline to our findings, Attaia et al. (1998) reported non-significant differences in dressing percentage of Japanese on diets varying in energy levels. Likewise, Dairol

et al. (2010) fed DWM to birds and concluded that higher dressing percentage obtained on low energy level diet and vice versa. On other side, (Mosaad & ibn 2009) reported increase in dressing percentage of birds on high energy diets. Like our findings, similar concept given in their study by Attia and Al-Harathi (2015) who concluded 20% date waste in finisher diets had no adverse influences on carcass parameters in birds.

Birds may give different results or remain un-influenced in case of blood profile or serum biochemistry on different types of diets or their respective levels. Our findings also showed inconsistent results in values of blood parameters of quails fed DWM by replacing conventional energy source i.e., maize grain. We found total protein, total lipids increased with increase in inclusion level of DWM up to 25% DWM while it decreased to minimum in birds fed diet containing 35% DWM however, total cholesterol level remained same on all diets including blood calcium and blood phosphate levels. We recorded maximum blood glucose level in birds fed 25% DWM and least in birds fed with diet containing 35% DWM. In partial agreement to our findings, Mosaad and ibn (2009) fed different levels of energy diets and found no significant difference in serum cholesterol, blood calcium and phosphate levels however, they reported linear increased in total lipids with increase in energy level in the diets. Sumilar to our findings, they also found significant difference in blood glucose levels on different diets. Generally, the Inconsistency in blood chemistry of birds fed different diets may occur due to many factors i.e., sampling time (Ferrer et al., 1994), birds species, genetic line, sex difference, digestion and absorption efficiency, internal rhythms (Perez-Rodriguez et al., 2008), ingredients composition of diets, Capture and restraining of birds (Lierz and Hafez, 2005). Similar to our findings, Jassim (2010) reported significant differences in total protein and blood glucose level on diet fed date waste at 150g/kg. Further, inline to our findings, they also not found any difference in total cholesterol level of birds fed similar energy and nitrogen level diets. Like our findings, similar concept given in their study by Attia and Al-Harathi (2015) who concluded that 20% DWM in diets had no adverse effect on blood serum constituents.

Conclusions

It is concluded that Japanese quails showed maximum growth performance (feed intake, weight gain and feed conversion ration) on diet containing 25% DWM by replacing with maize grain. Carcass yield and blood glucose were also found maximum on diet with 25% inclusion of DWM. In total cholesterol, blood calcium, and blood phosphate, no difference was found between control and DWM diets.

Recommendations

It is recommended that DWM may be incorporated in the diet of growing quails (from 1-4 week) up to 25% by replacing conventional grain source. Further studies required to be conducted for incorporation of DWM for finishing period and egg laying. The studies on other locally available non-conventional feed resources may also be required to carried out for optimal utilization of resources.

REFERENCES

- Aggoor, F., Attia, Y. A., & Qota, E. M. A. (2000). A study on the energetic efficiency of different fat sources and levels in broiler chick vegetable diets. *Journal of Animal and Poultry Production*, 25(2), 801-820.
- Ambigaipalan, P., & Shahidi, F. (2015). Date seed flour and hydrolysates affect physicochemical properties of muffin. *Food bioscience*, 12, 54-60.
- Ani, C., & Ovbiagele, B. (2009). Elevated red blood cell distribution width predicts mortality in persons with known stroke. *Journal of the neurological sciences*, 277(1-2), 103-108.
- Attia, A. A., El-Hindawy, M. M., Ismail, I. E., & Salama, A. A. (2017). Effect of azzawi date waste meal with or without avizyme supplementation on growth performance of japanese quail. *Zagazig Journal of Agricultural Research*, 44(6), 2607-2619.
- Attia, Y. A., & Al-Harathi, M. A. (2015). Effect of supplementation of date waste to broiler diets on

- performance, nutrient digestibility, carcass characteristics and physiological parameters. *Poultry Science*, 79, 2015.
- Baliga, M. S., Baliga, B. R. V., Kandathil, S. M., Bhat, H. P., & Vayalil, P. K. (2011). A review of the chemistry and pharmacology of the date fruits (*Phoenix dactylifera* L.). *Food research international*, 44(7), 1812-1822.
- Di Cagno, R., Filannino, P., Cavoski, I., Lanera, A., Mamdouh, B. M., & Gobbetti, M. (2017). Bioprocessing technology to exploit organic palm date (*Phoenix dactylifera* L. cultivar Siwi) fruit as a functional dietary supplement. *Journal of functional foods*, 31, 9-19.
- Diab, K. A. S., & Aboul-Ela, E. (2012). In vivo comparative studies on antigenotoxicity of date palm (*Phoenix dactylifera* L.) pits extract against DNA damage induced by N-Nitroso-N-methylurea in mice. *Toxicology international*, 19(3), 279.
- Duncan, D. B. (1955). Multiple range and multiple F tests. *biometrics*, 11(1), 1-42.
- Ferrer, M., Amat, J. A., & Viñuela, J. (1994). Daily variations of blood chemistry values in the Chinstrap Penguin (*Pygoscelis antarctica*) during the Antarctic summer. *Comparative Biochemistry and Physiology Part A: Physiology*, 107(1), 81-84.
- Flachowsky, G., Schafft, H., & Meyer, U. (2012). Animal feeding studies for nutritional and safety assessments of feeds from genetically modified plants: a review. *Journal für Verbraucherschutz und Lebensmittelsicherheit*, 7(3), 179-194.
- Ismail, B., Haffar, I., Baalbaki, R., & Henry, J. (2008). Physico-chemical characteristics and sensory quality of two date varieties under commercial and industrial storage conditions. *LWT-Food Science and Technology*, 41(5), 896-904.
- Jassim, J. M. (2010). Effect of using date by-product with enzyme on performance and blood parameter of broiler. *International journal of poultry science*, 9, 895-897.
- Jridi, M., Souissi, N., Salem, M. B., Ayadi, M. A., Nasri, M., & Azabou, S. (2015). Tunisian date (*Phoenix dactylifera* L.) by-products: Characterization and potential effects on sensory, textural and antioxidant properties of dairy desserts. *Food Chemistry*, 188, 8-15.
- Kamel, E. R., Mohammed, L. S., & Abdelfattah, F. A. (2020). Effect of a diet containing date pits on growth performance, diet digestibility, and economic evaluation of Japanese quail (*Coturnix coturnix japonica*). *Tropical animal health and production*, 52(1), 339-346.
- Kulkarni, S. G., Vijayanand, P., & Shubha, L. (2010). Effect of processing of dates into date juice concentrate and appraisal of its quality characteristics. *Journal of food science and technology*, 47(2), 157-161.
- Lierz, M., & Hafez, H. M. (2005). Sex-related differences in plasma chemistry reference values in stone curlews (*Burhinus oedicephalus*). *The Veterinary Record*, 157(3), 91.
- Martín-Sánchez, A. M., Ciro-Gómez, G., Sayas, E., Vilella-Esplá, J., Ben-Abda, J., & Pérez-Álvarez, J. Á. (2013). Date palm by-products as a new ingredient for the meat industry: Application to pork liver pâté. *Meat science*, 93(4), 880-887.
- Morne, P. (2017). *Facts and Trends SA: Agriculture. Production vs Demand*, South Africa, Pretoria, 1-3.
- Mosaad, G. M. M., & Iben, C. (2009). Effect of dietary energy and protein levels on growth performance, carcass yield and some blood constituents of Japanese quails (*Coturnix coturnix japonica*). *Die Bodenkultur*, 60(4), 39-46.
- Nadeem, M., Rehman, S. U., Anjum, F. M., & Bhatti, I. A. (2011). Textural profile analysis and phenolic content of some date palm varieties. *J. Agric. Res*, 49(4), 525-539.
- National Research Council. (1994). *Science and judgment in risk assessment*.
- Omoikhoje, S. O., Bamgbose, A. M., & Aruna, M. B. (2008). Replacement value of unpeeled cassava rootmeal (UCRM) for maize in weaner rabbit diets. *Nigerian journal of animal production*, 35(1), 63-68.
- Pérez-Rodríguez, L., Alonso-Alvarez, C., Martínez-Haro, M., & Viñuela, J. (2008). Variation in plasma

biochemical parameters in captive adult red-legged partridges (*Alectoris rufa*) during daylight hours. *European Journal of Wildlife Research*, 54(1), 21-26.

Rogers, D. W. O., Kawrakow, I., Seuntjens, J. P., Walters, B. R. B., & Mainegra-Hing, E. (2003). NRC user codes for EGSnrc. NRCC Report PIRS-702 (Rev. B).

Steel, Z., & Blaszczynski, A. (1998). Impulsivity, personality disorders and pathological gambling severity. *Addiction*, 93(6), 895-905.

Suherman, A. (2015). Pengaruh penambahan probiotik *Lactobacillus* plus bentuk tepung sebagai aditif pakan terhadap penampilan produksi burung puyuh (Doctoral dissertation, Universitas Brawijaya).

Tenenbaum, H. R., & Callanan, M. A. (2008). Parents' science talk to their children in Mexican-descent families residing in the USA. *International Journal of Behavioral Development*, 32(1), 1-12.